

PROBLEMS FACED BY STREET VENDORS IN COIMBATORE CITY

Dr. V. Sridevi, Associate Professor, Department of Commerce, Sri Krishna Adithya college of Arts and Science, Kovaipudur, Coimbatore

Ms. Akshaya UJ, III B COM IT, Sri Krishna Adithya college of Arts and Science, Kovaipudur, Coimbatore

ABSTRACT

This study provides an overview of the problems faced by street vendors in Coimbatore City, aiming to shed light on the challenges they encounter in their daily operations. Street vending plays a crucial role in the urban economy, providing affordable goods and services to the public. It is a global phenomenon and the most visible aspect. Like other informal sector, street vending is characterized by low level of income, easy of entry, self-employed and it involves large number of people. The study examines socio economic condition and problems faced by the street vendors in Coimbatore city. This study involves that 55% are street vendors, government of India passed the bill about street vendors 2022 for standard life style. This research selected 122 respondents from Coimbatore city adopting convenient sampling and study in descriptive natures. It's noted that the street vendors follow the street vending policies and they get the licenses from the authorized officials. Addressing the multifaceted challenges faced by street vendors requires a holistic approach encompassing legal reforms, access to financial services, and investment in supportive infrastructure. Recognizing the socioeconomic contributions of street vending and fostering inclusive urban policies are essential steps towards empowering vendors and fostering more equitable and vibrant urban spaces sanitation facilities, undermines the health and dignity of street vendors and their customers alike.

Key Words: Street Vendors, Problems, Challenges and Government Policy.

Introduction

Street vending is an important source of employment for many unskilled men and women from rural to urban backgrounds (Tshuma and Jari 2013). It is a boon for the rural poor to generate employment (Mishra, 2011). Street vending will be increasing and the demand for space will also expand in future (Ramanath Jha, 2016). According to the Ministry of Housing

and Urban Poverty Alleviation, there are approximately 10 million street vendors in India (2019, September 27) (Bhowmik, 2001) Ramanath Jha. (2018) reports that the statistical estimation of street vendors are different and conflicting as “The Street Vendors (Protection of Livelihood and Regulation of Street Vending) Act, 2014” calculates a maximum of 2.5 percent of a city’s population as street vendor

An evening walk often leads us to the vendors selling fragrant jasmine flowers, vegetables, fruits, hot bondas and bajis. Street vending has been a part of our culture and tradition. Traditionally, during the time of the festival and seasonal time street vendors mostly in the form of selling different products like fruits, flowers, vegetables, and other eatables on the road side. Street vendors form an important part of the socio-cultural and economic life since time immemorial. These vendors have been a part of our lives, which till date continues.

However, street vendors often face numerous obstacles that hinder their ability to thrive and contribute to the local economy. This study utilizes a qualitative research approach, employing interviews and surveys to gather data from street vendors in Coimbatore City. The findings of this study highlight the need for policy interventions and support mechanisms to address the challenges faced by street vendors. By understanding the specific problems faced by street vendors in Coimbatore City, policymakers, urban planners, and relevant stakeholders can develop targeted strategies to improve the working conditions and livelihoods of street vendors.

OBJECTIVES

- ✓ To identify the social economic characteristics of the street vendors in Coimbatore City
- ✓ To identify the major constrains that vendor faces while operating the business
- ✓ To suggest policy intervention that helps to mitigate challenges of street vendors by the government.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present study is descriptive by nature. The research is based on both primary and secondary data. Primary data were collected through Interview Schedule and Questionnaires. Secondary Data were collected through Websites and Online Journals, Published Reports and Review of

Literature from Published Articles. The sampling is selected by using Convenient Sampling and the sample size is confined as 123. Respondents have been selected on street who was selling various types of goods in Coimbatore City.

CATEGORIES OF STREET VENDORS

- 'Mobile Vendors' includes those vendors carrying baskets, hung on balancing poles on their shoulders ,bicycle , tricycle, and motorcycle, as well as trucks or vans selling commissioned food stuffs such as vegetables , blankets and ice creams.
- 'Semi-Mobile' vendors include those selling from carts, which may be stationary or moved from one site to another.
- 'Stationary' vendors may sell their foods from permanent structures at certain points in the city or even in front of shops, providing tables and chairs for immediate consumption.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

- **John Walsh (2010)** founded that the “Common Problem Faced for Vendors” involved excess of stock (especially perishable items like fruits and vegetables) at the end of the day. He also pointed out that since some of the goods being traded are seasonal in nature, therefore there is threat of the vendors falling below the poverty line in out of season periods, unless suitable alternatives can be identified and sourced.
- **Dr. M. N. Mohamed Abusali Sheik (2016)**, in their study “Problems Faced by Street Vendors”, in this modern world street vendors playing an important role in sacrificing the consumer’s day to day needs. Most of the Consumers are dependent on them. In Earlier days, men only take part in the business but nowadays women’s are also take part in it and also facing lots of problem than men. Majority of the street vendors have started the business on their own owing to self-motivation and interest with their own minimum capital investment, and thus it’s a form of sole selling business. Hence, they have some future plan expand their business.

- **Dr. G. Jayanti, Baranipriya. A and Sreeanadan (2020)** in their study examined the “Socio Economic Condition and Problems Faced by the Street Vendors” in Coimbatore city. The result reveals that, female's contribution in this sector is lesser than the male respondents and they were facing problems like health issues, wastage of unsold goods, and insecurity in employment. Therefore, the government should take some corrective measures to improve their socio- economic and living conditions of street vendors.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

TABLE 1 – Socio Economic Characteristics of Street Vendors

S.No.	Category	No. of respondents	%
1.	Age		
	10-15	9	7.3
	15-25	70	56.9
	25-35	34	27.6
	35 and above	10	8.1
2.	Gender		
	Male	48	39
	Female	74	60.2
	Transgender	1	0.8
3.	Educational Qualification		
	UG	48	39
	Student	27	22
	Diploma	25	20.3
	PG	19	15.4
	Uneducated	4	3.3
4.	Marital Status		
	Married	24	19.5
	Unmarried	99	80.5
5.	Earnings		
	10000-20000	36	29.3

	20000-30000	35	28.5
	30000-40000	34	27.6
	Above 40000	18	14.6

Source: Primary data

TABLE 2: Vending Products

Products	No of respondents	%
Fast foods	39	28.5
Fruits	35	31.7
Vegetables	29	23.6
Flowers	11	8.9
Others	9	7.3
Total	123	100

Source: Primary data

TABLE 3: Number of Years in Street Vending

Age	No of respondents	%
Less than a year	45	36.6
1-3 years	42	34.1
3-5 years	25	20.3
Above 5 years	11	8.9
Total	123	100

Source: Primary data

TABLE 4: Reason for Street Vending

Reason	No of respondents	%
Low investment	41	33.3
Family occupation	39	31.7
Additional Income	40	32.5
Others	18	14.6
Total	123	100

Source: Primary data

TABLE 5 Problems Faced by Street Vendors

Problems	No of respondents	%
Lack of workplace	33	26.8
Lack of social security	56	45.5
Too much competition	37	30.1
Evictions by private shop guards	12	9.8
Total	123	100

Source: Primary data

TABLE 6: Awareness about Street Vendor Schemes

Awareness	No of respondents	%
Yes	46	37.4
No	53	43.1
Maybe	24	19.5
Total	123	100

Source: Primary data

TABLE 7: Improvement Measures

Measures	No of respondents	%
Policy formulations	55	44.7
Need of funds	34	27.6
Working place arrangement	22	17.9
Permitting license	7	5.7
Others	5	4.1
Total	123	100

Source: Primary data

TABLE 8: Challenges Faced by Street Vendors

Challenges	No of respondents	%
Financial assistance	47	38.2
Legal guidance	48	39
Training in business	23	18.7
Improved relations with local authorities	10	8.1
Total	123	100

Source: Primary data

TABLE 9: Source of getting Finance

Particulars	No of respondents	%
Friends or Family	48	38.2
Savings or Personal fund	47	39
Microfinance Institutions	19	15.4
Others	9	7.3
Total	122	100

Source: Primary data

FINDINGS

The major problems of the street vendors are Lack of social security, doesn't aware of street vendors Scheme, faces safety or health concerns, moderate weather condition issues and too much of competition. The main challenges are faced by street vendors are financial assistance and legal guidance.

SUGGESTIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

- The general suggestions for improvement of street vendors include permitting license and need for workplace.
- Sustained and continuous efforts are needed to improve the education, health and employment conditions of the street vendors.
- The government can assist them financially for their business activities at free rate of interest and government can extend the subsidy to the street vendors, especially for vending perishable items.
- Awareness programmes on environment and waste disposal management can be given to the street vendors.

CONCLUSION

Street vendors are important part of the informal sector not only because of their numbers but because of crucial roles they play in preserving their sector. The objective of the paper is to identify the causes behind street vending, challenges faced by street vendors, highlight the importance of street vendors, what measures are taken by the government to provide facilities to the street vendors in the working conditions, social protection and life skill development to improve the level of profitability. Government provides street vending policies for street vendors; however, the street vendors are not aware of such policies. This study reveals that the best way for the planners to address this issue is to formalize the street vendors by issuing licenses. India has witnessed an increased in street vendors, the government is indifferent to specific needs of this sector. Street vendors perform an important role in providing services to the urban population especially the poor. Street vending and petty trading activities from the essential core of informal economic sectors in developing nations help in generating income with minimized investment of financial capital and without requiring large human capital.

REFERENCES

Nitika Diwakar and Renu Anand (2014) ‘Socio-Economic Study on Women Street Vendors’, Newmen International Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies, Vol-1, 12, pp.125 – 132.

Njaya, T., Strategies for Daily Survival: The Role of Social Capital among Street Vendors of Harare Metropolitan. IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS), 20(7). 2015

Njaya, T., Employment creation or sheer survival? Case of street vendors of Harare Metropolitan in Zimbabwe. Global Journal of Advanced Research, 1(2), 2014.pp. 264-274.

Selvakumar, V.Sathyalakshmi and K.Siva Murugan (2014), ‘Problems and Prospects of Street Vendors in Sivakasi’, Asian Review on Social Sciences (ARSS)Vol.3, No.2, pp – 34 -41

Harpreet Kaur and Sanpreet kaur (2017), A Study on Quality of Work Life of Street Vendors of Khana’, Bizad Bytes, Vol.8, Iss- 1, pp. 59- 63